

1 **Reorganization of Agulhas Extension meanders explains sea surface height trends since 1993**

2 **C. M. Aiken^{1,2,3}, A. Meyer^{1,2,3} and C. Chapman^{3,4,5}**

3 ¹Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies, University of Tasmania, Hobart, Australia

4 ²Centre of Excellence for Climate Extremes, Hobart, Australia

5 ³Centre of Excellence for Weather of the 21st Century, Hobart, Australia

6 ⁴CSIRO Environment, Hobart Marine Laboratories, Hobart, Australia

7 ⁵School of Science, The University of NSW - Canberra, Canberra, Australia

8

9

10

11 Corresponding author: Chris Aiken (christopher.aiken@utas.edu.au)

12

13 **Key Points:**

14 • Large decadal trends in the southwest Indian Ocean sea surface height result from shifts
15 in the meandering path of the Agulhas Extension

16 • The meandering of the Agulhas Extension is well captured by a linear inverse model.

17 • Major downstream trends are driven by upstream meander disturbances that propagate
18 eastward in a standing wave pattern

19

20 **Abstract**

21 Large multi-decadal trends of alternating sign in the sea surface height of the southwest Indian
22 Ocean reflect a reorganization of the meandering path of the Agulhas Extension – the main
23 conduit connecting the tropical Pacific and Indian Ocean to the Southern Ocean. The apparent
24 weakening of the standing wave pattern characteristic of the Agulhas Extension above the
25 Southwest Indian Ridge owes to changes in the spatial distribution of the meander crests and
26 troughs. Using a linear inverse model trained on sea surface height data, we show that these
27 trends are dynamically connected via wave propagation to changes in the meandering further
28 upstream.

29

30 **Plain Language Summary**

31 Satellite observations over the past 30 years reveal large changes in sea surface height along
32 the Agulhas Extension, a major ocean current marking the boundary between the warm Indian
33 Ocean and the colder Southern Ocean. These trends are much larger than global sea-level rise
34 and come from shifts in the path of the current's meanders - the bends, crests, and troughs
35 along its route. We show that the strongest trends, found near the Southwest Indian Ridge, are
36 linked to changes that occurred upstream. Using a statistical model trained on satellite data, we
37 find that patterns of meander growth and decay can propagate along the current, shaping how
38 it evolves over weeks to months. Although this type of model is more typically used for large-
39 scale climate modes like El Niño, it is surprisingly effective at capturing the evolution of this
40 fast, unstable ocean current, revealing dynamics that are otherwise hard to detect. Two types
41 of upstream disturbances that act as 'precursors' are identified. These propagating signals help
42 explain why long-term trends appear where they do, and suggest that the recent reorganization
43 is unlikely due to random variability. Because such currents strongly influence heat and carbon
44 transport, these changes can have global repercussions.

45

46 **1 Introduction**

47 The Western Boundary Current Extensions are fast, eastward-flowing currents in the
48 midlatitudes. They result from the geostrophic balance between the Earth's rotation and the
49 polewards decrease in the height of the ocean's surface. As they form a barrier between warm
50 salty subtropical water and cool fresh subpolar water, they play an important role in
51 modulating the how heat is transported polewards (e.g. Marshall 1997). The meandering and
52 eddies that form on the current provide the pathway for this transport, either directly through
53 the ocean (e.g. Vilela-Silva et al, 2024, Jayne and Marotzke, 2002; Griffies et al 2015), or
54 through air-sea heat exchange (Small et al., 2008; Seo et al 2023, Vilela-Silva et al, 2024). The
55 Agulhas Extension (AE), or Agulhas Return Flow, of interest here is the extension of the Agulhas
56 Current that flows along the eastern coast of Africa, and forms the main connection between
57 the Indo-Pacific and Southern Ocean (Figure 1). As such, changes in the AE have relevance for
58 Southern Ocean heat budgets and global climate.

59 Three decades of satellite altimetry reveal large trends in sea surface height in the
60 Western Boundary Current Extensions, of up to 30 cm/decade and far exceeding the global sea-
61 level rise signal of ~3 cm/decade (Church and White, 2006; Frederikse et al. 2018) (Figure 1a).
62 These large trends owe to relatively small movements in the position of the currents and their
63 associated sharp sea surface height gradients. In the Kuroshio Extension of the North Pacific,
64 observed sea level trends indicate a shift toward reduced meander variability and a polewards
65 migration of the jet axis (Joh et al 2022). By contrast, in the AE a remarkable zonal wave
66 pattern occurs in the sea surface height trends along its axis (Figure 1b). The trends, of up to
67 15 cm/decade, are suggestive of changes in the amplitude and location of the meander crests
68 and troughs, but without a poleward shift of the main axis (Figure 1d; Meyer et al. unpublished
69 manuscript).

70 Meanders develop in the AE due to dynamic instability of the current after it separates
71 from the African coast (e.g. Kuo, 1973). Interaction with a number of bathymetric features
72 along its path appears to leave an imprint on the distribution of the meanders. The Agulhas
73 Plateau in particular, despite barely rising above a depth of 3000 m, appears to anchor the

74 meander crests and troughs to some degree, such that a marked meander pattern remains in
75 the mean of sea surface height (Figure 1d). Currents such as the AE whose meander crests and
76 troughs have preferential locations are often referred to as “standing meanders” (Figure 1b)
77 (Thompson and Garabato., 2014; Zhang et al., 2023; Liu et al. 2024), but it is important to note
78 that individual meander crests and troughs do, in fact, propagate, both eastwards and
79 westwards (see Figure 2). In fact, the AE path indicated by the mean state is not even the most
80 common state of the system; the meander state rarely and only briefly resembles the standing
81 wave pattern shown in the mean. On the contrary, the meanders evolve over time-scales of
82 weeks to months, and there is clear evidence for their propagation upstream and downstream
83 relative to the strong eastwards flow. Large meanders commonly pinch to form cut-off eddies,
84 that may be subsequently reabsorbed by the AE, adding further complexity to its meandering
85 path. As such, the sea surface height trends shown in Figure 2b do not necessarily reflect a
86 gradual change in the “normal” state of the standing meander, but rather a change in the
87 frequency of occurrence of the complex propagating wave species that inhabit the AE.
88 Moreover, wave propagation along the main axis of the AE suggests that the trends along the
89 axis of the AE may be interlinked.

90 The wave pattern in the sea surface height trend is generally in phase with that of the
91 AE standing meander, but with a significant difference: west of the Southwest Indian Ridge,
92 (approximately 3000 km downstream from the Agulhas retroflexion point and west of
93 meander trough T3, as labelled in Figure 1d), the trends suggest increasing mean meander
94 amplitude, while to the east (meander crests and troughs T4 and T5), the trends indicate mean
95 meander flattening.

96 Using a Linear Inverse Model (LIM) – an empirical dynamical model trained to
97 reproduce observed covariance, in this case of sea surface height - we show that these
98 opposing trends in apparent meander amplitude to the east and west may be linked. LIMs have
99 been used broadly in systems for which the dynamics can be approximated as the linear
100 interaction between a small number of oscillatory modes (e.g. Penland and Magorian, 1993).
101 Examples of their use include the analysis of tropical and extratropical weather and climate

102 modes (Penland and Sardeshmukh 1995, Aiken et al. 2013, Alexander et al. [2008](#); Newman
103 2007; Cavanaugh et al. [2015](#); Capotondi and Sardeshmukh [2015](#); Huddart et al. [2016](#); Newman
104 and Sardeshmukh [2017](#)), and in a ecology (Capotondi et al. 2022, Van Oevelen 2010). After
105 describing the modes of variability of the AE meander field, we demonstrate that a LIM
106 captures the observed meandering behavior, and finally analyse the LIM to deduce the
107 propagation of signals across the AE.

108

109 **2 Data and Methods**

110 2.1 Sea Surface Height

111 Sea surface height over the 1993-2023 period was obtained from the E.U. Copernicus Marine
112 Service Information “Global Ocean Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights” product. This product uses
113 optimal interpolation to combine along-track satellite altimeter data from the various available
114 overlapping missions of the past three decades. We use the product’s “adt” variable, which is
115 the sea level anomaly relative to a 20 year mean (see open research statement).

116 2.2 Linear Inverse Model construction

117 While the basic mechanism for current meandering is well established (e.g. Kuo 1973), the
118 process will be impacted by factors such as the velocity shear and strain, the density
119 stratification, the local bathymetry, and fluctuations in the strength of the wind and of the
120 current itself. Here, rather than assume which of these factors are involved in the meandering
121 of the AE, we attempt to infer the effectively linear component of the dynamics from the
122 observations. The prevalence of coherent, propagating patterns in the sea surface height field
123 (Figure 2a) suggests that it may be possible to represent the apparently complex meandering
124 behaviour of the AE by linear wave growth and propagation. Idealised linear models have
125 shown success in reproducing features of meandering jets (Abernathy and Cessi 2014).

126 LIMs have been used broadly for providing dynamical insights into, and even skillful
127 predictions of, geophysical systems whose dynamics can be approximated as linear, for

128 example, when the non-linearities can be treated as additional Gaussian noise (Farrell and
129 Ioannou 1996). Detailed descriptions of the procedure for LIM construction are given in several
130 papers (e.g., Newman et al. 2003; Newman 2007; Penland and Sardeshmukh 1995), and so
131 details of our construction of the LIM are left for the appendix. Here we summarise that a LIM,
132 built on the reduced state space spanned by the first 50 Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs)
133 of sea surface height and calculated based on the 25 day covariance, captures the evolution of
134 the AE meander field remarkably well over lead times of months. That is,

135

136

$$\mathbf{x}(\tau) \approx e^{\mathbf{L}\tau}\mathbf{x}(0), \quad (1)$$

137

138 where \mathbf{x} is the component of the sea surface height data represented by the first 50 EOFs and \mathbf{L}
139 is the LIM, for lead times τ . The EOFs were calculated from the anomalous sea surface height,
140 after removing the linear trend and seasonal cycle. As such, the LIM does not “know” about the
141 trend. The choice to use 50 EOFs represents a trade-off between resolving the main modes of
142 jet meandering while preventing over-fitting by maintaining the system strongly over-
143 determined.

144

2.3 Linear Inverse Model Optimal Precursors

145

146

By representing the dynamics of AE meandering as a linear model, we can learn much about
the system behavior through standard matrix analysis. For example, we can use the singular

147 value decomposition of the “propagator” $\mathbf{R}(\tau) = e^{\mathbf{L}\tau}$ to diagnose which patterns are most
 148 predictable over a lead time τ (Farrell and Ioannou, 1996)

149

$$150 \quad \mathbf{x}(\tau) = \mathbf{R}(\tau)\mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{USV}^T\mathbf{x}(0). \quad (2)$$

151

152 The singular value decomposition organises the action of the propagator into a set of
 153 independent linear transformations from the columns of \mathbf{V} to the columns of \mathbf{U} . The diagonal
 154 matrix \mathbf{S} gives the coefficient of the transformation. For example, the projection of the initial
 155 state $\mathbf{x}(0)$ onto the first column of \mathbf{V} produces a final state given by the first column of \mathbf{U}
 156 multiplied by the first element of \mathbf{S} . As a result, the original linear system can be approximated
 157 by retaining only those singular vectors that grow the most, as these are the initial conditions
 158 most likely to offer prediction skill. The right singular vectors of a dynamical operator are
 159 sometimes referred to as the optimal perturbations (e.g. Penland & Sardeshmukh, 1995) or, as
 160 here, the optimal precursors (e.g. Capotondi & Sardeshmukh, 2015). In this case, our interest is
 161 not in how much the optimal precursors grow, but rather which patterns of AE meandering do
 162 they represent.

163 **3 Results**

164 **3.1 Empirical Orthogonal Functions**

165 The EOFs used to construct the reduced order LIM were calculated from the anomalies of the
 166 detrended, 5-day mean sea surface height for the 1993-2023 period (see section 2.1). If the
 167 meanders of the AE were truly stationary, we would expect that a large part of the variance
 168 would be explained by a single EOF corresponding to variations in the amplitude of the standing
 169 wave pattern. Instead, we find that the AE supports a large number of modes of meandering,
 170 each explaining a small fraction of the variance. The first 50 EOFs (of a total of 2272 5-day
 171 means in the 31 year record) used as the basis to construct the LIM explain a little more than
 172 25% of the variance in our domain, and the first EOF slightly less than 1%. We show below that,

173 nonetheless, the LIM constructed from these 50 EOFs simulates well the dominant patterns of
174 AE meandering that are apparent in the observations (cf. Figures 2b and 2c; details presented in
175 3.3).

176 The four leading EOFs are depicted in Figure 3a-d, together with their power spectral density.
177 The first two EOFs largely correspond to the approximately bimonthly Agulhas ring formation
178 process (Duncan, 1968; Lutjeharms & Gordon, 1987; Pichevin et al., 1999, Richardson 2007),
179 involving a westward propagation of a sea surface height anomaly tripole from the Agulhas
180 Plateau back towards the point of retroflexion, south-west from the southern tip of the African
181 continent. Arrow A in Figure 2c indicates an example of this quasi-regular westward phase
182 propagation, which is discussed further in section 3.3a. Significant differences do exist between
183 the first two EOFs; the EOF1 pattern involves greater covariance with the Southwest Indian
184 Ridge sector of the AE, and has additional power at interannual periods than the EOF2 pattern,
185 which would suggest some covariance between the formation of Agulhas rings and the state of
186 the AE further east.

187 The third and fourth EOFs (Figure 3c and 3d) describe predominantly interannual variations that
188 are most heavily weighted to the Southwest Indian Ridge sector of the AE. Of note is the fact
189 that EOF4 resembles the zonal phase of the observed sea surface height trend, especially in the
190 Southwest Indian Ridge region where the trends are largest (contours of the trend are overlain
191 on each EOF in Figure 3.) This is notable because the linear trend was removed before
192 calculating the EOFs. As such, **rather than a gradual readjustment of the meandering pattern
193 or a fundamental change in the AE's dynamical stability, these trends appear to correspond
194 to adjustments in the natural modes of meandering. Specifically, part of the sea surface
195 height trends may be explained by an increase in the likelihood of EOF4 to occur in its
196 positive phase over recent decades.**

197 3.2 Linear Inverse Model simulations

198 The LIM constructed from the EOFs can be used to simulate the meandering behaviour of the
199 AE using equation (1) (see Figure 2b). The fact that the LIM has significant skill at simulating the

200 AE (beating climatology and persistence forecasts over lead times up to 12 months; Figure S1 in
201 Supporting Information), suggests that AE meandering over timescales of months can be
202 usefully described by linear wave growth and propagation. An example time-series of sea
203 surface height anomalies from a stochastically forced LIM simulation contains various of the
204 prominent modes of propagation seen in the observations (cf Figure 2bc) such as the slow
205 westwards and eastwards phase propagation and the rapid eastwards group propagation (see
206 details in Supporting Information).

207 We first use the LIM to test whether the observed trends could be explained simply by natural
208 decadal fluctuations in these modes of meandering. To this end, we test how frequently a 30
209 year trend in EOF4 - that corresponding most closely to the spatial pattern of the trend -
210 appears with a value greater than the observed trend in stochastically forced LIM simulations.
211 From an ensemble of 10,000 such simulations, 62 reproduced trends in EOF4 that exceeded the
212 observed trend – i.e. at a rate of approximately 1 in 200 (Figure S3 in Supporting Information).

213 **This suggests that it is unlikely, albeit not impossible, that the observed sea surface height**
214 **anomaly trends could occur by chance due to the natural modal variations captured by the**
215 **LIM.**

216 3.3 Linear Inverse Model Optimal Precursors

217 As described in section 2.3, a singular value decomposition of the LIM is used to reveal which
218 states of AE meandering are most strongly linked to prior states. The “maximum amplification
219 curve” of the LIM (Figure 4i) presents the maximum growth rate of sea surface height
220 anomalies (i.e. the largest singular value in \mathbf{S} in equation (2)) as a function of lead time. The
221 presence of two local maxima in the curve, at times of approximately 20 and 60 days, suggests
222 two distinct mechanisms exist that can preempt growing sea surface height anomalies over
223 these two time-scales. As will be discussed below, these two mechanisms resemble patterns
224 commonly seen in the sea surface height altimetry observations.

225 a. Optimal precursor over 20 days

226 The most rapid growth of sea surface height anomalies in the LIM occurs over a period of 20
227 days (Figure 4i) and can be understood as the “pinching” of the retroflection of the AE (i.e. the
228 closure of sea surface height contours) to form Agulhas rings. As depicted in Figure 4, the
229 pinching is preceded by negative sea surface height anomalies propagating southwestwards in
230 the Agulhas, that then bridge across the retroflection to the AE. It is this bridging action that
231 results in the ubiquitous westward propagation of anomalies in the AE path from the Agulhas
232 Plateau towards the retroflection point, an example of which is marked by the arrow labelled
233 “A” in Figure 2a. This process is consistent with the role of the Agulhas Current meanders
234 known as “Natal Pulses” in initiating Agulhas ring formation (Backeberg et al., [2008](#); van
235 Leeuwen et al., [2000](#)).

236

237 b. Optimal precursor over 60 days

238 The optimal precursor for a 60 day lead time (Figure 4e) takes the form of a train of five sea
239 surface height anomalies of alternating sign, corresponding to the formation of a series of
240 meanders in the AE traversing the Southwest Indian Ridge sector. The pattern is a standing
241 wave - the locations of the centres of the sea surface height anomalies do not move over the 60
242 days, but the location of maximum amplitude propagates eastwards, starting west of the
243 Southwest Indian Ridge at meander trough T3 (Figure 1d) and terminating to its east at
244 meander trough 4 (Figure 4c,h).

245

246 This eastward group velocity of the 60 day optimal precursor matches well the eastward
247 propagating signal in the observations (arrow C in Figure 2ab). Similar small amplitude standing
248 wave signals with eastwards group velocity are ubiquitous in the full altimetry record (Figure S4
249 in Supporting Information). This process also occurs commonly in the stochastically forced LIM
250 simulations presented in Section 3.2 (arrows in Figure 2b), and in ocean models (Figure S5 in
251 Supporting Information). The group speed of these eastward signals is on the order of
252 expected translation speeds within the AE, which runs at an average of 0.75 m/s at the Agulhas
253 retroflection and slowly weakens downstream (Lutjeharms & Ansorge 2001).

254

255 The 60 day optimal precursor has significant predictive skill in the original sea surface height
256 observations. The projection of the sea surface height anomalies onto the final state of the 60
257 day optimal precursor correlates strongly with the projection onto its initial state 60 day earlier
258 (Figure 4j). We refer to the “positive state” of the 60 day optimal precursor as that depicted in
259 Figure 4e, and the “negative state” as its converse. Instances where the path of the AE
260 meanders in the form indicated by Figure 4e, be it in the positive or negative sense, almost
261 always precede meandering akin to Figure 4h of the corresponding sign over the following
262 months.

263

264 Moreover, it is apparent in Figure 4j that in recent decades the negative state of the 60 day
265 optimal precursor has become more infrequent, and the positive state more frequent (blue
266 dots corresponding to earlier times in the observational record are more likely to be found in
267 the negative quadrant of the figure, and red dots, later times, in the positive quadrant). The
268 fact that there are recent instances of the negative state, and early instances of the positive
269 state, that obey the same relationship, suggests that the relationship holds throughout the
270 three decade record. Negative forcing always tends to produce a negative response.

271

272 The 60 day optimal precursor describes a process whereby a perturbation to the jet in the
273 vicinity of T3 grows as it propagates downstream, reaching its maximum amplitude two months
274 later at T4. This is the location where the strongest trends in sea surface height occur, and
275 comparison of the mature state of the 60 day optimal precursor to the sea surface height
276 trends (indicated by contours in Figure 4) reveals a strong resemblance between the wave
277 structures of the two patterns. Moreover, an anomalous increase in the meander trough
278 amplitude at T3 leads to an anomalous decrease in the meander trough amplitude at T4.

279 **Simply put, in the 60 day optimal precursor, larger meanders upstream suppress or displace**
280 **the meander immediately downstream, consistent with the conflicting pattern of standing**
281 **meander amplitude seen in the sea surface height trends.** Thus the picture emerges that the
282 large sea surface height trends found at T4, above the Southwest Indian Ridge, are consistent
283 with a change in frequency of occurrence of the 60 day optimal precursor.

284

285 We restate that the linear trend was removed prior to construction of the LIM – i.e. the LIM
286 does not “know” about the trend - and yet the LIM captures processes that can explain the
287 trends. **This supports the hypothesis that the trends at T4 owe to a readjustment of the jet**
288 **meandering - a dynamical response to the trends immediately upstream.** That is, the
289 increase of the mean amplitude of the standing meander located at T3, leads to a decrease of
290 the mean standing meander amplitude at T4.

291

292 **5 Conclusions**

293 The prominent trends in sea surface height in the Agulhas Extension meander field over the
294 1993-2022 period appear to owe to a reorganisation of the complex meandering flow and its
295 associated strong sea surface height gradients. Although referred to as a *standing* meander,
296 propagating signals along the current’s zonal axis, both eastwards and westwards, are a notable
297 feature of the sea surface height variability. Our analysis suggest that the propagating standing
298 wave patterns also commonly observed, in the form of transient rapid eastward group
299 propagation, flavour the long-term trends in the Agulhas Extension’s meandering path.

300

301 We find that Agulhas Extension meandering over timescales of months can be well represented
302 by a Linear Inverse Model (LIM) – an empirical dynamical model trained to reproduce the
303 lagged covariance of anomalous sea surface height. The success of the LIM in forecasting
304 Agulhas Extension meandering over monthly time-scales highlights the importance of linear
305 wave growth and propagation in the variability of its path. **Through analysis of the LIM, two**
306 **optimal precursors were identified that skillfully predict prominent aspects of the**
307 **meandering:**

308

309 *Agulhas ring formation over 20 days:* While not our primary interest, the analysis shed light on
310 the process of Agulhas ring formation. The 20 day optimal precursor reveals that, although
311 each Agulhas ring is preceded by large sea surface height anomalies propagating west from the
312 Agulhas Plateau (arrow A in Figure 2a), the process is initiated by disturbances akin to Natal

313 Pulses propagating southwards in the Agulhas Current and bridging across the retroflexion. It
314 is notable that we find no evidence that these extreme fluctuations in the path of the jet caused
315 by Agulhas ring formation have an impact upon the meanders further downstream.

316
317 *Meander Growth over 60 days:* The LIM's 60 day optimal precursor corresponds to the
318 ubiquitous standing wave signals with rapid eastward group velocity seen commonly in the
319 observations. We find that this process links the large observed trends in sea surface height in
320 the vicinity of the Southwest Indian Ridge. Episodes where the jet meanders out of phase with
321 the standing meander pattern above the Southwest Indian Ridge tend to be preceded by an
322 increase in the amplitude of the meander found immediately upstream. Although this
323 manifests as a linear trend towards reduced amplitude of the standing meander above the
324 Southwest Indian Ridge, our results suggest that it is driven by increased frequency of large
325 meander amplitudes upstream causing the locations of the meander crests to shift
326 downstream. That is, the standing meander flattening above the Southwest Indian Ridge
327 (Figure 1c) is related to the location of meandering becoming more variable, and hence less
328 apparent in the mean.

329
330 **Thus we suggest that 1) anomalies in the path of the Agulhas Extension above the Southwest**
331 **Indian Ridge are driven by anomalous meandering occurring upstream a number of months**
332 **earlier; and that 2) a trend in the sign of the anomalous meandering occurring upstream has**
333 **driven the large trends in the Southwest Indian Ridge region meander over the three decades**
334 **since 1993.**

335
336 These results are essentially statistical, and do not identify the physical explanations. Changes
337 in the meandering behavior could be driven by internal changes in the density or shear that
338 impact the dynamical stability, or through changed surface forcing. The degree to which
339 bathymetry controls the character of meandering is also not completely clear. While
340 downstream propagation is common to its east, the Agulhas Plateau appears to insulate much
341 of the Agulhas Extension from the extreme fluctuations in its path caused by Agulhas ring

342 formation. There is some evidence for interannual covariance across the entire Agulhas
343 Extension in the leading EOF, but the Agulhas Plateau appears to prevent such disturbances
344 from impacting the meandering to its east. For the 60 day optimal precursor, the eastwards
345 group velocity across its standing wave pattern implies a role of advection by the Agulhas
346 Extension.

347

348 Finally, simulations with the LIM provide evidence that the reorganisation observed in the
349 Agulhas Extension meander field over the past three decades is inconsistent with natural
350 internal variability. The persistence of the diagnostic 60-day optimal precursor relationship
351 across the altimetry era indicates that these dynamics are likely to continue under current
352 conditions. In addition to being a simple yet effective diagnostic tool, the LIM approach
353 provides a novel perspective for identifying emerging dynamical shifts and can be readily
354 applied to other current systems. Given that meandering in Western Boundary Current
355 Extensions plays a critical role in regulating poleward heat and tracer fluxes, generating eddies,
356 and shaping air-sea coupling, changes in the Agulhas Extension meander field have implications
357 for regional ocean stratification, storm-track modulation, and the storage and release of heat
358 and carbon. These emerging shifts highlight the potential for broader climate impacts, both
359 locally and remotely, and underscore the importance of continued investigation into the
360 evolving dynamics of Western Boundary Current Extensions.

361

362

363

364

365 **Figure 1.** a) Linear trend in altimetric sea level for the period 1993 to 2023. The black rectangle
 366 marks the study region, illustrated in panels b-d. b) Linear trend in altimetric sea surface height
 367 relative to geoid in the Agulhas Extension region. Overlain arrows indicate the corresponding
 368 trend in geostrophic velocities. Note that the legend is offset by 3 cm/decade, corresponding
 369 approximately to the global sea level rise signal. c) Mean altimetric sea surface height relative to

370 geoid, and corresponding geostrophic velocity. d) Bathymetry of the southwest Indian Ocean and
371 changes in the Agulhas Extension, as given by the mean location of the 0.6 m sea surface height
372 contour over the two periods indicated. The major bathymetric features shown are the Agulhas
373 Plateau (AP), the Madagascar Plateau (MP), the Southwest Indian Ridge (SWIR), the Del Canto
374 Rise (DCR), and the Kerguelen Plateau (KP). The first five standing meander crests and troughs
375 are labelled for reference.

376

378 **Figure 2.** Hovmöller plots of (a) the latitude anomaly in the path of the Agulhas Extension, as
379 approximated from the 0.6 m sea surface height contour, as a function of longitude and time.
380 The wave propagation observed in this two year period shown is typical of the three decade
381 altimetry record (see Supporting Information). Examples of the propagation of meander latitude
382 anomalies are marked: A) fast westwards phase propagation from the Agulhas Plateau towards
383 the retroflection region; B) slow westwards phase propagation; C) fast eastwards group
384 propagation; and D) slow eastwards phase propagation; (b) the sea surface height anomaly along
385 the axis of the Agulhas Extension for an arbitrary 2 year segment taken from the stochastically
386 forced LIM simulation; and (c) the evolution of the sea surface height anomalies along the axis
387 of the Agulhas Extension corresponding to the development of the 60 day optimal precursor.
388 Arrows labelled C in each panel mark a consistent mode of anomaly propagation between
389 observations and the LIM simulation.
390

391

392 **Figure 3.** (a-d) Maps of the first four EOFs of detrended observed sea surface height (colour
393 shading) in the Agulhas Extension region and their associated power spectral density (inset).
394 Selected contours indicate the sea surface height trend pattern from Fig 1b. Depths greater than
395 3000 m are shaded (grey).

397 **Figure 4.** Maps of the structure and development over time of the LIM optimal 20 day precursor
398 (a-d) and the 60 day optimal precursor for the Agulhas Extension region (e-h). Depths greater
399 than 3000 m are shaded (grey). Select contours indicate the observed sea surface height trend
400 pattern from Fig. 1b. (i) Maximum amplification curve for perturbations to the LIM. (j)
401 Projection of the final state of the 60 day optimal precursor (panel g) onto the observed sea
402 surface height plotted as a function of the projection of the initial state of the 60 day optimal
403 precursor (panel e), 60 days earlier. Colour indicates time from 1993 (blue colors) to 2023 (red
404 colors).

405

406

407 **Acknowledgments**

408 The authors wish to acknowledge the financial support of the Australian Government through
409 the Centre for Excellence in Climate Extremes CE170100023 and Centre for Excellence in
410 Weather of the 21st Century CE230100012. AM was also supported by the Australian Research
411 Council Discovery Early Career Research Award projects DE200100414. We acknowledge and
412 are grateful for the freely available Copernicus Sea Surface Height data.

413

414

415 **Open Research**

416 The sea surface height data were sourced from the E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information
417 (CMEMS) Marine Data Store (MDS) “Global Ocean Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights” product at
418 <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00149>.

419

420

421 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

422 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

423

424 **References**

- 425 Abernathey, R., & Cessi, P. (2014). Topographic enhancement of eddy efficiency in baroclinic
426 equilibration. *Journal of physical oceanography*, 44(8), 2107-2126.
- 427 Alexander, M. A., Matrosova, L., Penland, C., Scott, J. D., & Chang, P. (2008). Forecasting Pacific
428 SSTs: Linear inverse model predictions of the PDO. *Journal of Climate*, 21(2), 385-402.
- 429 Aiken, C. M., & Navarrete, S. A. (2014). Coexistence of competitors in marine
430 metacommunities: environmental variability, edge effects, and the dispersal niche. *Ecology*,
431 95(8), 2289-2302.
- 432 Aiken, C. M., Santoso, A., McGregor, S., & England, M. H. (2013). The 1970's shift in ENSO
433 dynamics: A linear inverse model perspective. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 40(8), 1612-1617.
- 434 Backeberg, B. C., Johannessen, J. A., Bertino, L., & Reason, C. J. (2008). The greater Agulhas
435 Current system: An integrated study of its mesoscale variability. *Journal of Operational*
436 *Oceanography*, 1(1), 29-44.
- 437 Capotondi, A., & Sardeshmukh, P. D. (2015). Optimal precursors of different types of ENSO
438 events. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42(22), 9952-9960.
- 439 Capotondi, A., Newman, M., Xu, T., & Di Lorenzo, E. (2022). An optimal precursor of Northeast
440 Pacific marine heatwaves and Central Pacific El Niño events. *Geophysical Research*
441 *Letters*, 49(5), e2021GL097350.
- 442 Cavanaugh, N. R., Allen, T., Subramanian, A., Mapes, B., Seo, H., & Miller, A. J. (2015). The skill
443 of atmospheric linear inverse models in hindcasting the Madden–Julian Oscillation. *Climate*
444 *Dynamics*, 44(3), 897-906.
- 445 Church, J. A., & White, N. J. (2006). A 20th century acceleration in global sea-level
446 rise. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33(1).
- 447 Duncan, C. P. (1968). An eddy in the subtropical convergence southwest of South Africa. *Journal*
448 *of Geophysical Research*, 73(2), 531-534.

- 449 Farrell, B. F., & Ioannou, P. J. (1996). Generalized stability theory. Part I: Autonomous
450 operators. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 53(14), 2025-2040.
- 451 Frederikse, T., Jevrejeva, S., Riva, R. E., & Dangendorf, S. (2018). A consistent sea-level
452 reconstruction and its budget on basin and global scales over 1958–2014. *Journal of*
453 *Climate*, 31(3), 1267-1280.
- 454 Griffies, S. M., Winton, M., Anderson, W. G., Benson, R., Delworth, T. L., Dufour, C. O., ... &
455 Zhang, R. (2015). Impacts on ocean heat from transient mesoscale eddies in a hierarchy of
456 climate models. *Journal of Climate*, 28(3), 952-977.
- 457 Jayne, S. R., & Marotzke, J. (2002). The oceanic eddy heat transport. *Journal of Physical*
458 *Oceanography*, 32(12), 3328-3345.
- 459 Joh, Y., Delworth, T. L., Wittenberg, A. T., Cooke, W. F., Rosati, A. J., & Zhang, L. (2022). Stronger
460 decadal variability of the Kuroshio Extension under simulated future climate change. *npj*
461 *Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 5(1), 63.
- 462 Kuo, H. L. (1973). Dynamics of quasigeostrophic flows and instability theory. *Advances in*
463 *Applied Mechanics*, 13, 247-330.
- 464 Liu, X., Meyer, A., & Chapman, C. C. (2024). Characteristics and trends of the Campbell Plateau
465 meander in the southern ocean: 1993–2020. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 129(2),
466 e2023JC019876.
- 467 Lutjeharms, J. R. E., & Gordon, A. L. (1987). Shedding of an Agulhas ring observed at
468 sea. *Nature*, 325(6100), 138-140.
- 469 Lutjeharms, J. R. E., & Ansorge, I. J. (2001). The Agulhas return current. *Journal of Marine*
470 *Systems*, 30(1-2), 115-138.
- 471 Marshall, D. (1997). Subduction of water masses in an eddying ocean. *Journal of Marine*
472 *Research* 55, (2). https://elischolar.library.yale.edu/journal_of_marine_research/2223

- 473 Newman, M. (2007). Interannual to decadal predictability of tropical and North Pacific sea
474 surface temperatures. *Journal of climate*, 20(11), 2333-2356.
- 475 Penland, C., & Sardeshmukh, P. D. (1995). The optimal growth of tropical sea surface
476 temperature anomalies. *Journal of Climate*, 8(8), 1999-2024.
- 477 Penland, C., & Magorian, T. (1993). Prediction of Niño 3 sea surface temperatures using linear
478 inverse modeling. *Journal of Climate*, 6(6), 1067-1076.
- 479 Pichevin, T., Nof, D., & Lutjeharms, J. (1999). Why are there Agulhas rings?. *Journal of physical*
480 *oceanography*, 29(4), 693-707.
- 481 Richardson, P. L. (2007). Agulhas leakage into the Atlantic estimated with subsurface floats and
482 surface drifters. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 54(8), 1361-1389.
- 483 Seo, H., O'Neill, L. W., Bourassa, M. A., Czaja, A., Drushka, K., Edson, J. B., ... & Wang, Q. (2023).
484 Ocean mesoscale and frontal-scale ocean-atmosphere interactions and influence on large-scale
485 climate: A review. *Journal of climate*, 36(7), 1981-2013.
- 486 Small, R. D., deSzoeke, S. P., Xie, S. P., O'Neill, L., Seo, H., Song, Q., ... & Minobe, S. (2008). Air-
487 sea interaction over ocean fronts and eddies. *Dynamics of Atmospheres and Oceans*, 45(3-4),
488 274-319.
- 489 Thompson, A. F., & Naveira Garabato, A. C. (2014). Equilibration of the Antarctic Circumpolar
490 Current by standing meanders. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 44(7), 1811-1828.
- 491 Van Leeuwen, P. J., de Ruijter, W. P., & Lutjeharms, J. R. (2000). Natal pulses and the formation
492 of Agulhas rings. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 105(C3), 6425-6436.
- 493 Van Oevelen, D., Van den Meersche, K., Meysman, F. J., Soetaert, K., Middelburg, J. J., & Vézina,
494 A. F. (2010). Quantifying food web flows using linear inverse models. *Ecosystems*, 13(1), 32-45.

495 Vilela-Silva, F., Bindoff, N. L., Phillips, H. E., Rintoul, S. R., & Nikurashin, M. (2024). The impact of
496 an Antarctic Circumpolar Current meander on air-sea interaction and water subduction. *Journal*
497 *of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 129(7), e2023JC020701.

498 Zhang, X., Nikurashin, M., Peña-Molino, B., Rintoul, S. R., & Doddridge, E. (2023). A theory of
499 standing meanders of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current and their response to wind. *Journal of*
500 *Physical Oceanography*, 53(1), 235-251.